

ESTIMATION OF ATMOSPHERIC AND TRANSPONDER SURVEY ERRORS WITH A NAVIGATION KALMAN FILTER

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Abstract

The Completely Integrated Reference Instrumentation System (CIRIS) is an aircraft Inertial Navigation System (INS) aided with range and range-rate measurements from precisely surveyed ground transponders. The full-ordered Kalman filter "truth" model for this system is developed with the goal of increasing the error estimation accuracy of the CIRIS Kalman filter. This model includes the correlated errors in the range measurement due to atmospheric delay uncertainties and transponder position survey-errors.

This paper presents the basic structure of the 127-state "truth" model Kalman filter. The random bias shaping filter model for the transponder position survey-errors and the first order Markov shaping filter model for the atmospheric propagation delays are developed. The full-ordered Kalman filter based on the CIRIS "truth" model is used to process empirical data from a CIRIS flight. The time histories of selected correlated measurement errors' means, covariances, and range residuals are plotted and analyzed with respect to the filter's estimate of position and velocity errors, as well as the aircraft trajectory. Finally, the initial conclusions drawn from this data are presented.

Introduction

The Completely Integrated Reference Instrumentation System (CIRIS) is a term that refers to a transponder aided Inertial Navigation System (INS) currently used by the Air Force for testing new aircraft navigation systems. The Office of Primary Responsibility (OPR) for this system is the Central Inertial Guidance Test Facility (CIGTF), 6585th Test Group, Air Force Systems Command (AFSC), Holloman AFB, NM. The basic idea is to fly the navigation system to be tested, called the test article, and the CIRIS system aboard an aircraft through a trajectory of interest in the CIRIS transponder range. Data from both systems is recorded during flight and compared to determine how closely the test system follows the CIRIS system. The CIRIS system is considered to be much more accurate than the navigation systems currently being tested, thus the CIRIS data serves as a reference for determining performance of current aircraft navigation systems.

The current CIRIS system is capable of providing the aircraft's latitude and longitude with an accuracy of 13 feet (ft) 1σ ; altitude with an accuracy of 40 ft 1σ ; north and west velocity with an accuracy 0.1 ft/sec (fps) 1σ ; and vertical velocity with an accuracy of 0.4 fps 1σ (4). The high accuracy of the CIRIS system is attributed to the accuracy of transponder measurement aiding. Ground based transponders are installed over a test range that can cover the length and width

of the United States land mass. The positions of these transponders are surveyed precisely; CIGTF estimates the accuracy of the surveys at approximately 3-6 ft 1σ . During testing the CIRIS system receives an accurate measurement of the host aircraft's range and range-rate, to transponders of interest. The range and range-rate measurements from each transponder are optimally combined with the CIRIS INS data, in an extended Kalman filter (EKF), to produce an accurate estimate of the INS error. The INS output is corrected to produce an accurate estimate of the aircraft position and velocity. The initial development of the CIRIS Kalman filter was completed by the Intermetrics corporation (5) and the range/range-rate measurement system (RRS) by the Cubic corporation (3). The physical concept of the CIRIS system is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Physical Concept of CIRIS

The research goal is to develop a more complete "truth" model for the errors in this system. The "truth" model is defined in terms of the stochastic differential equation that models all known error characteristics in the INS and the aiding measurements. The full-ordered EKF is used to establish the baseline filter accuracy in estimating these errors. This model is also the foundation for development of the advanced CIRIS system which will include range measurements from the Global Positioning System (GPS).

Current CIRIS Kalman Filter

The error in the transponder range measurement is dominated by the effects of atmospheric propagation delays and transponder survey-errors. These errors are estimated by the full-ordered EKF. One phase of this research is the development of accurate stochastic models that describe these errors. This paper presents the stochastic models developed and their initial performance characteristics as analyzed in the context of the full-ordered EKF structure.

Kalman Filter Equations

This section states the Kalman filter equations with only a brief comment. The reader is referred to texts such as Reference (6) for further explanation and derivation. The stochastic error differential equation is in the form:

$$\delta\dot{\underline{X}}(t) = \mathbf{F}(t) \delta\underline{X}(t) + \underline{W}(t) \quad (1)$$

$$E\{\underline{W}(t)\} = \underline{0} \quad (2)$$

$$E\{\underline{W}(t) \underline{W}^T(t+\tau)\} = \mathbf{Q}(t) \delta\tau \quad (3)$$

The vector $\delta\underline{X}(t)$ represents the navigation stochastic errors which are defined as the difference between the true and the INS indicated states. The matrix $\mathbf{F}(t)$ represents the linearized system error dynamics (1). The vector \underline{W} is a gaussian, "white," zero-mean noise vector with strength \mathbf{Q} (6:275).

The measurement error equation is in the form:

$$\delta Z_k(t_k) = \mathbf{H}_k(t_k) \delta\underline{X}(t_k) + \mathbf{V}_k(t_k) \quad (4)$$

$$E\{\mathbf{V}_k(t_k)\} = 0 \quad (5)$$

$$E\{\mathbf{V}_k(t_k) \mathbf{V}_k(t_j)\} = \begin{cases} \mathbf{R}_k(t_k) & t_i = t_j \\ 0 & t_i \neq t_j \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

The matrix \mathbf{H} relates the measurement to the error states. \mathbf{V} is a Gaussian, "white," zero-mean noise with strength \mathbf{R} . In this application the measurement equation is a scalar equation (6:275). For the filter presented $k=1,2$; where $k=1$ is the range aiding measurement and $k=2$ is the range-rate aiding measurement.

The Kalman filter propagation equations, in continuous time form, are (6:275):

$$\delta\hat{\underline{X}}(t/t_{i-1}) = \mathbf{F}(t) \delta\hat{\underline{X}}(t/t_{i-1}) \quad (7)$$

$$\hat{\mathbf{P}}(t/t_{i-1}) = \mathbf{F}(t) \mathbf{P}(t/t_{i-1}) + \mathbf{P}(t/t_{i-1}) \mathbf{F}^T(t) + \mathbf{Q}(t) \quad (8)$$

These are integrated from initial conditions $\delta\hat{\underline{X}}(t_{i-1}^+)$ and $\hat{\mathbf{P}}(t_{i-1}^+)$, the last Kalman filter update. The algorithm is started from an appropriate set of initial values.

Finally, the standard form of the Kalman filter update equations is (6:275):

$$\underline{\mathbf{K}}(t_i) = \mathbf{P}(t_i) \mathbf{H}^T(t_i) [\mathbf{H}(t_i) \mathbf{P}(t_i) \mathbf{H}^T(t_i) + \mathbf{R}(t_i)]^{-1} \quad (9)$$

$$\delta\hat{\underline{X}}(t_i^-) = \delta\hat{\underline{X}}(t_i^+) + \underline{\mathbf{K}}(t_i) [\delta Z_k(t_i) - \mathbf{H}(t_i) \delta\hat{\underline{X}}(t_i^+)] \quad (10)$$

$$\mathbf{P}(t_i^-) = \mathbf{P}(t_i^+) - \underline{\mathbf{K}}(t_i) \mathbf{H}(t_i) \mathbf{P}(t_i^+) \quad (11)$$

The $[\delta Z_k(t_i) - \mathbf{H}(t_i) \delta\hat{\underline{X}}(t_i^+)]$ in Eq (10) is commonly referred to as the residual.

This section describes the major characteristics of the current CIRIS filter model. The current CIRIS system uses a 13 state EKF. The errors being estimated are defined by the 13 state error vector shown in Eq (12). The error states modeled in this filter represent a subset of the error states required to completely model the CIRIS INS linearized error dynamics and baro-altimeter aiding error states. Note that this subset of error states contains none of the correlated errors in the INS (gyro drift, gyro bias, accelerometer bias, etc.) or the range measurement (transponder survey, atmospheric, etc.) (1).

$$\delta\underline{X} = \begin{bmatrix} \delta L \\ \delta \lambda \\ \delta H \\ \phi_N \\ \phi_E \\ \phi_Z \\ \delta V_N \\ \delta V_E \\ \delta V_Z \\ S_1 \\ S_2 \\ S_3 \\ S_4 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \text{Latitude Error} \\ \text{Longitude Error} \\ \text{Altitude Error} \\ \text{North Tilt} \\ \text{East Tilt} \\ \text{Vertical Tilt} \\ \text{North Velocity Error} \\ \text{East Velocity Error} \\ \text{Vertical Velocity Error} \\ \text{Baro Aiding 1} \\ \text{Baro Aiding 2} \\ \text{Baro Aiding 3} \\ \text{Baro Aiding 4} \end{bmatrix} \quad (12)$$

The effect of this low order EKF is illustrated by examining the transponder line-of-sight range residuals. The Kalman filter residuals are a direct indication of how well the Kalman filter model represents the real-world data. If the model perfectly matches all the spectral characteristics of the real world data, the residual data process will be a "white" Gaussian sequence of mean zero and covariance $\mathbf{H}(t_i) \mathbf{P}(t_i) \mathbf{H}^T(t_i) + \mathbf{R}(t_i)$ (6). Since it is a function of the filter's covariance, it is independent of the real world measurements and can be calculated "a priori". The square root of each diagonal covariance matrix element is designated the 1σ value (6:226-231).

An example of a "white," zero mean Gaussian noise and unit strength is shown in Figure 2. In the physical world a "white" residual can not be attained. However, the closer the Kalman filter residuals approach this "white" process, with the applicable 1σ magnitude, the better the Kalman filter performance, which in turn implies a higher model accuracy for the system.

The current CIRIS filter output for the aircraft trajectory used in this analysis, presented later in this paper, is available. One representative transponder range residual is presented. This transponder is also used in the analysis of the full-ordered filter performance. The range residual for the transponder designated T-185 is shown in Figure 3.

The 1σ value designated in the plot is predicted by the filter for each measurement update. This quantity is:

$$1\sigma(t_i) = \sqrt{\mathbf{H}(t_i) \mathbf{P}(t_i) \mathbf{H}^T(t_i) + \mathbf{R}(t_i)} \quad (13)$$

where:

- \mathbf{H} = Filter measurement gradient row-matrix
- \mathbf{P} = Filter covariance matrix
- \mathbf{R} = Scalar filter measurement noise strength

Figure 2. Gaussian "White" Noise

The predicted statistics for the range residual shown in Figure 3 are a mean of zero and a 1σ value of approximately 14 ft. The actual statistics of the range residual shown are a mean of +11.02 ft and a 1σ value of 5.51 ft; the residual is biased and exhibits significant correlated errors indicating a lack of "whiteness" (as compared to Figure 2). It is clear that filter performance is degraded by unmodeled correlated errors. The bulk of these correlated error effects, exhibited by the current CIRIS filter residuals, are attributed to the unmodeled transponder-survey and atmospheric errors.

Figure 3. Typical Current CIRIS Transponder Residual

An attempt is made in the CIRIS computer to remove some of the atmospheric error. A deterministic open-loop correction is made to the line-of-sight range measurement data before it is processed by the filter. This correction is:

$$R_M = R_M - e_R \quad (14)$$

R_M = Corrected Range Measurement

R'_M = Raw Range Measurement

e_R = Error Due To Atmospheric Effects

The atmospheric error (e_R) is attributed entirely to the nonzero refractivity of the troposphere. The troposphere is defined as the region of the atmosphere from sea-level to about 70,000 ft. In the current CIRIS filter, the refractivity above sea level is approximated with an exponential function based on altitude above sea level (H), atmospheric scale factor (H_s), and sea level refractivity (N_s). This equation is:

$$N = N_s e^{-\frac{H}{H_s}} \quad (15)$$

The CIRIS range correction (e_R) calculation is based on a complicated function relating refractivity, altitude, and length of measurement cycle. This algorithm description can be found in Reference (5:6.3-14, 6.3-15). However, as indicated by the residual characteristics defined in Figure 2, this correction is inadequate for the desired estimation accuracies. Developing a stochastic atmospheric error model and allowing the EKF to estimate this error can improve the system performance.

Transponder Survey-Error Model

The transponder survey-error is a correlated measurement error and must be modeled with a stochastic shaping filter. All correlated measurement errors present in the range measurement are depicted in the Earth-Centered-Earth-Fixed (ECEF) frame (E-frame) in Figure 4. The transponder survey-errors are designated $\delta X'_T$, $\delta Y'_T$, and $\delta Z'_T$.

Figure 4. Depiction of Correlated Measurement Errors

The transponder survey-errors represent the limitations of Defense Mapping Agency (DMA) geodetic survey accuracy. The resulting errors are constant in time and relatively small in magnitude. In this research the survey-errors are modeled in the X', Y', and Z' (E-frame) axes. This error is "best" represented by a random bias (constant) shaping filter. The three transponder survey-errors coordinatized in the E-frame are represented by the vector defined:

$$\delta \underline{P}_T = \begin{bmatrix} \delta X'_T \\ \delta Y'_T \\ \delta Z'_T \end{bmatrix} \quad (16)$$

The stochastic differential equations are now developed for the errors shown in Eq (16). The transponder position errors (δX_T , δY_T , δZ_T) are modeled as random biases with an initial mean of 0 ft and initial 1σ value of 5 ft. The describing stochastic differential equation is:

$$\delta \dot{\underline{P}}_T(t) = \underline{0} \quad (17)$$

$$\delta \hat{\underline{P}}_T(t_0) = \underline{0} \quad (18)$$

$$P_{\delta \underline{P}_T}(t_0) = \begin{bmatrix} 25 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 25 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 25 \end{bmatrix} \quad (19)$$

The Kalman filter identifies and estimates these errors based on the modeled spectral characteristics. The autocorrelation function and the power spectral density (PSD) characteristics are shown in Figure 5. The initial mean is designated m_0 and the initial covariance by P_0 .

Figure 5. Random Bias Shaping Filter Characteristics (6:183)

These three states are augmented to the INS error vector and included in the filter's range measurement equation. The dynamics are augmented to the INS $F(t)$ matrix. The full-ordered model is defined in a later section.

Atmospheric Error Model

The atmospheric error is another correlated measurement error and requires a stochastic shaping filter model. This error is depicted as a line-of-sight range error in Figure 4. This error is attributed to the nonzero refractivity of the troposphere integrated along the line-of-sight path. Since deterministically corrected range measurements are used by the full-ordered EKF, the filter is estimating the error residue in this correction is defined by Eq (14).

The refractivity (N) is a function of the atmospheric index of refraction (n):

$$N = (1-n) \times 10^6 \quad (20)$$

A nonzero refractivity (N) corresponds to an index of refraction (n) greater than 1 and a decrease in the electromagnetic wave propagation velocity (v) from the speed of light (c). This decrease in velocity results in an erroneous increase in the line of sight range measurement. The basic equation is (5:6.3-1, 6.3-3):

$$v = \frac{1}{n} c \quad (21)$$

The refractivity is a time varying quantity based on the atmospheric temperature (T), water vapor content (e), and atmospheric pressure (P). This quantity is (5:6.3-4):

$$N = \frac{77.6 P(t)}{T(t)} + \frac{37,300 e(t)}{T(t)^2} \quad (22)$$

A line of sight error occurs in the range measurement due to atmospheric conditions changing the index of refraction and resulting in propagation delays. The resulting time-varying error magnitude is relatively small. This error is "best" represented by a first-order Markov process shaping filter. The Cubic RRS atmospheric error is modeled as a first order Markov time varying error with a correlation time of approximately 300 seconds, noise strength of 0.1667 ft²/sec, initial mean of 0 ft, and initial 1σ value of 5 ft. The correlation time for this model is derived from several data recorded in a static test at CIGTF. Range data was recorded from several transponders at different distances. After removing the true range, the power spectral density (PSD) on this error data indicated an average correlation time of 300 seconds. The stochastic differential equation and the filter initial conditions are:

$$\delta \dot{E}_{ATM}(t) = -\frac{1}{300} \delta E_{ATM}(t) + W_{ATM} \quad (23)$$

$$\delta \hat{E}_{ATM}(t_0) = 0 \quad (24)$$

$$P_{\delta E_{ATM}}(t_0) = 25 \quad (25)$$

$$E\{W_{ATM}(t)\} = 0 \quad (26)$$

$$E\{W_{ATM}(t)W_{ATM}(t+\tau)\} = 0.1667 \delta(\tau) \quad (27)$$

This is an exponentially time-correlated process. The autocorrelation function and power spectral density characteristics are shown in Figure 6. The correlation time is represented by T, the mean is zero, and the initial covariance by σ^2 . This state is augmented to the INS dynamic system stochastic differential equation and included in the filter's range measurement equation. The full-ordered model is defined in a later section.

Full-Ordered Kalman Filter Structure

The first 85 states of the full-ordered EKF represent the errors in the CIRIS INS. The CIRIS uses a Litton LN-39 Air Force standard INS. This 85 state error model is taken directly from the comprehensive Litton engineering analysis report defining the error characteristics of this system (7). The error states contained in this model consist of the three position errors, three platform tilts, three velocity errors, one wander angle error, three baro-altimeter INS aiding channel errors, 10 sensor correlated errors, 21 gyro bias errors, 29 accelerometer and bias errors, 9 thermal transient errors, and three gyro turn-around drift errors. The details of this INS model are not presented in this paper, but can be found in Reference (8).

Figure 6. First-Order Markov Characteristics (6:183)

There are 42 additional states required to model the correlated errors in the range and range-rate measurements. These error states consist of two transponder interrogator/receiver calibration errors (range loop and range-rate loop) common to all transponders, three transponder survey-errors (three axes of E-frame) and a line-of-sight atmospheric error for each transponder. These errors are augmented to the INS "truth" model stochastic differential equation to form the full-ordered "truth" model stochastic differential equations. The calibration range and range-rate random biases are assumed to be in the interrogator on the aircraft. Therefore, these errors are common to all the transponders interrogated and require only two states. The transponder survey-errors and atmospheric error are unique to each transponder. Although the atmospheric propagation error is expected to be somewhat correlated from one transponder line-of-sight to another, it is neglected in this analysis. Therefore, each transponder interrogated requires 4 unique states.

A typical CIRIS flight uses from 10 to 30 different transponders. It normally sequences through a 5-10 transponder window at a 1 Hz rate. It deletes/adds transponders to this window to optimize the transponder geometry. Providing 4 states for each transponder is computationally burdensome. To keep the computational load manageable, 4 states are provided for only 10 different transponders (maximum number possible in a window) for a total of 40 additional states. When a

transponder is deleted and replaced with a new one, the four rows and columns of the covariance matrix for the respective transponder error states are set to zero. The mean for each of the respective states is set to zero when the transponder is first used in the flight. However, the algorithm saves the mean of the current transponder before switching to a new transponder and if this transponder is encountered again in the flight, it reinitializes the error state means with the saved values. The covariance diagonal element for each of the four states is reinitialized to its initial value of 25 ft². With this procedure any number of transponders encountered during a flight are accommodated without additional states.

The 127-state (85+42) augmented stochastic differential equation is:

$$\delta\dot{\underline{X}}(t) = \mathbf{F}(\underline{X}, t) \delta\underline{X}(t) + \underline{W}(t) \quad (28)$$

$$\delta\underline{X} = \begin{bmatrix} \delta\underline{X}_{\text{INS}} \\ \delta\underline{X}_{\text{MEAS}} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{F} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{F}_{\text{INS}} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{F}_{\text{MEAS}} \end{bmatrix}, \quad \underline{W} = \begin{bmatrix} \underline{W}_{\text{INS}} \\ \underline{W}_{\text{MEAS}} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$\delta\underline{X}(t_0) = \underline{0} \quad (29)$$

$$\mathbf{P}_{\delta\underline{X}}(t_0) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{P}_{\text{INS}} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{P}_{\text{MEAS}} \end{bmatrix} \quad (30)$$

$$E\{\underline{W}(t_0)\} = \underline{0} \quad (31)$$

$$E\{\underline{W}(t_0)\underline{W}(t_0+\tau)\} = \mathbf{Q}(t_0)\delta(\tau) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{Q}_{\text{INS}} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{Q}_{\text{MEAS}} \end{bmatrix} \delta(\tau) \quad (32)$$

Note that the \mathbf{F} matrix is calculated based on $\hat{\underline{X}}$ which is the current best estimate of the true states. This full state vector is defined as:

$$\hat{\underline{X}} = \underline{X} - \delta\underline{X} \quad (33)$$

The details of this model are found in Reference (8).

The measurement equations are defined as:

$$\delta Z_1(t_i) = \delta Z_{\text{RANGE}}(t_i) = \mathbf{H}_R(\hat{\underline{P}}_A, \hat{\underline{P}}_T, t_i) \delta\underline{X}(t_i) + \mathbf{V}_R(t_i) \quad (34)$$

$$\hat{\underline{P}}_A = \underline{P}_A - \delta\hat{\underline{P}}_A$$

$$\hat{\underline{P}}_T = \underline{P}_T - \delta\hat{\underline{P}}_T$$

$$E\{\mathbf{V}_R(t_i)\} = 0$$

$$E\{\mathbf{V}_R(t_i)\mathbf{V}_R(t_j)\} = \begin{cases} \mathbf{R}_R & t_i = t_j \\ 0 & t_i \neq t_j \end{cases}$$

$$\delta Z_2(t_i) = \delta Z_{\text{RATE}}(t_i) = \mathbf{H}_{\text{RR}}(\hat{\underline{P}}_A, \hat{\underline{P}}_T, \hat{\underline{V}}_A, t_i) \delta\underline{X}(t_i) + \mathbf{V}_{\text{RR}}(t_i) \quad (35)$$

$$\hat{\underline{V}}_A = \underline{V}_A - \delta\hat{\underline{V}}_A$$

$$E\{\mathbf{V}_{\text{RR}}(t_i)\} = 0$$

$$E\{\mathbf{V}_{\text{RR}}(t_i)\mathbf{V}_{\text{RR}}(t_j)\} = \begin{cases} \mathbf{R}_{\text{RR}} & t_i = t_j \\ 0 & t_i \neq t_j \end{cases}$$

Eqs (34) and (35) are scalar equations. Again note that the best estimate of the full states are used to calculate the measurement gradient matrices (\mathbf{H}_R and \mathbf{H}_{RR}). The definitions of the \mathbf{H}_R and \mathbf{H}_{RR} matrices are not presented in this paper, but can be found in Reference (8). The Kalman filter is updated once a second with a measurement from one of the transponders.

The last quantity described is the residual of the Kalman filter. Because the measurements are nonlinear, the extended Kalman filter form of the residual equation is used. This equation replaces the residual quantity defined in Eq (10). This form is defined as:

$$r_1(t) = \hat{R}_C(\hat{P}_A, \hat{P}_T, t) + \delta \hat{E}_{CALR}(t) + \delta \hat{E}_{ATM}(t) - R_M(t) \quad (36)$$

$$r_2(t) = \hat{R}_C(\hat{P}_A, \hat{P}_T, \hat{V}_A, t) + \delta \hat{E}_{CALRR}(t) - \dot{R}_M(t) \quad (37)$$

The variables \hat{R}_C and \dot{R}_C are the nonlinear calculations of aircraft range and range-rate to transponder based on the optimal estimate of aircraft and transponder positions and aircraft velocity. The variables R_M and \dot{R}_M are the measurements from the RRS. The range and range-rate nonlinear equations are used with the best estimate of the full states. This form of the residual calculation takes into account the nonlinearities of the quantity and results in a better estimate of the true residual. This is in comparison with the linearized error residual update form (6).

The overall structure of the full-ordered filter is defined in this section to illustrate the complexity of the model and the method of augmenting the transponder survey and atmospheric errors. The details of this model are found in Reference (8).

Simulation

A CIRIS flight tape was provided by CIGTF. This data tape contains the INS position and velocity, barometric altimeter, range measurement, and delta range measurement data for the flight of approximately 4.5 hours. The tape also contains the error state means, error state covariances, and measurement residuals from the current CIRIS filter for this flight. The flight trajectory for this data is illustrated in Figure 7.

Figure 7. CIRIS Flight Trajectory

The CIRIS flight time is designated in seconds. It begins at time 26132 and ends at time 42000. Since the full ordered filter is computationally intensive and because most of the high dynamic maneuvers occur early in the flight, only the first 2.25 hours of the flight are processed by the filter beginning at 26132 and ending at 34000. The T=34000 point is shown in Figure 7. This simulation required 17 hours of CPU time on a VAX 8650 computer. The latitude vs longitude and altitude vs longitude position trajectory plots, including transponder locations, for the abbreviated CIRIS flight profile are shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8. CIRIS Abbreviated Flight Profile

The data from transponder T-185 is selected for detailed residual and correlated error analysis. The characteristics of this transponder are considered representative of all the transponders. Transponder T-185 is designated T-185 and circled in Figure 8.

The full-ordered EKF is coded into the Multimode Simulation for Optimal Filter Evaluation (MSOFE) software package (2) to conduct the simulation. This software package was developed by the Avionics Laboratory at Wright-Patterson AFB, Ohio. A FORTRAN program is used to transform the CIRIS flight tape data into data files used by MSOFE. The simulations are conducted on the AFIT's VAX 8650 computer system.

These data files are processed in MSOFE from takeoff at time 26132 to time 34000 (2.25 hours). The range and range rate measurements are updated from one transponder every second. A 7σ tolerance is used for residual monitoring. Any measurement greater than 7 times the predicted residual 1σ is rejected for both range and range rate measurements. This residual monitoring technique rejected 14% of the 16,060 range and range rate measurements from all transponders. This number of rejected measurements is considered acceptable and does not effect the overall quality of the filter error estimation accuracy. Only the range residual and correlated errors for transponder T-185 are investigated in this paper, the complete analysis is found in Reference (8).

Range Residual for Transponder T-185

The range residuals are a direct indication of how well the Kalman filter model represents the real world as explained in the "Current CIRIS" section. The full-ordered EKF range residual for transponder T-185 is shown in Figure 9. The 1σ designated curve is the filter prediction.

Figure 9. Full-Ordered Filter Range Residual

The predicted statistics of the range residual for this transponder are a mean of zero with a 1σ value of approximately 3 ft. The actual statistics are a mean of +0.28 ft with a 1σ value of 4.58 ft. This residual has a negligible bias and exhibits very few correlated error characteristics. The closer similarity to a "white" noise process is emphasized by a direct comparison of this range residual to the current CIRIS range residual shown in Figure 3. The improvement in the residual characteristics is attributed to using the EKF to estimate the transponder survey and atmospheric range measurement errors within the quality of the model accuracy.

The actual 1σ values for the full-ordered and current CIRIS filters are similar. This indicates that the magnitude of the random error in both filters is nearly the same. However, the full-ordered filter range residual characteristics are closer to the ideal (filter predicted) residual characteristics. Therefore, the position and velocity estimated errors predicted by the full-ordered filter based on the "truth" model are closer to the real world true errors than the current CIRIS filter error estimates.

Correlated Measurement Errors for Transponder T-185

Transponder T-185's error state means and 1σ values for the X' and Y' correlated measurement errors are shown in Figure 10. The aircraft trajectory with respect to this transponder is shown in Figure 8. The aircraft traverses the transponder vicinity to the South of its location. This geometric relationship is poor and the filter may have difficulty estimating these survey-errors in all 3 E-frame axes.

The final X' error attained a mean of -5 ft and a 1σ value of 2.6 ft. The Y' error attained a mean of -4 ft and a 1σ value of 4 ft. The two large transients apparent at times 29000 and 33000 are attributed to degraded observability due to poor geometry and large trajectory turns at these times. Initially the three elements of the survey-error are unobservable. However, as the aircraft-transponder line-of-sight geometry changes, three dimensional observability is accumulated in the EKF covariance matrix. The magnitude of these errors are reasonable for the survey-errors being estimated.

Figure 10. T-185 X' and Y' Correlated Errors

Transponder T-185's error state means and 1σ values for the Z' and atmospheric (ATM) correlated measurement errors are shown in Figure 11. The Z' error attained a mean of -13 ft and a 1σ value of 3.5 ft. The characteristics of this error are very similar to the X' and Y' errors shown in Figure 10. Again the magnitude of this error is reasonable indicating the filter is estimating the actual real world survey-error.

This data indicates the transponder survey-errors are observable and the filter's random bias shaping filter model is estimating the error magnitudes. The geometric relationship of the line-of-sight vectors (aircraft to transponder) with transponder survey-error vector determines how well the error is estimated. Therefore, the ultimate accuracy of the survey-error estimates is directly related to the aircraft/transponder geometric relationship time history as described above.

The atmospheric error shown in Figure 11 depicts the Kalman filter effort to estimate the line of sight error in the range measurement due to propagation delays caused by atmospheric conditions. This is a time varying error and is a function of weather conditions and aircraft distance to the transponder. This error is attributed to the changing atmospheric index of refraction (n) which causes a decrease in the electromagnetic wave propagation velocity, erroneously causing a increase in the measured range magnitudes. Therefore, the filter estimated atmospheric error is expected to be negative. However, the CIRIS computer makes an open loop correction to each range measurement before it is processed by the filter. This allows the atmospheric error to vary between negative and positive magnitudes. This characteristic is clearly observable in the atmospheric error time histories.

Figure 11. T-185 Z' and Atmospheric Correlated Errors

The atmospheric error state mean for transponder T-185 varies from -10 to +17 ft with an average 1σ value of 3.5 ft. The magnitudes and shapes of the error time-histories are reasonable for this type of error. This error is observable and the first-order Markov shaping filter allows the filter to accurately estimate this error.

Although these results were obtained using a single forward pass of the EKF, much improved estimation of the survey and atmospheric errors is expected when a backward pass is added in a smoother operation. This implementation is commonly referred to as an optimal smoother algorithm (6).

Conclusions

Based on the residual and correlated error characteristics, the shaping filter models chosen for the transponder survey and atmospheric improve the Kalman filter performance. The time histories of these error indicate that they are observable and the EKF is estimating their magnitudes. The absolute accuracy of these estimates can not be determined at this time. However, in an attempt to quantify the increase in performance of the full-ordered EKF filter, position estimates are differenced with the current CIRIS system. Results of this comparison are presented in Table 1.

Table 1
Position Error State Differences

Position Error States	Mean Difference		1σ Value Difference	
	Mean ft	1σ Value ft	Mean ft	1σ Value ft
Latitude	+3.37	7.98	+0.03	0.42
Longitude	+5.73	10.29	0.00	0.39
Altitude	+25.66	63.86	+6.82	5.04

Note: All differences are "Truth" - CIRIS

The difference in the 1σ values are negligible. However, there are differences in the means of approximately 3 ft in latitude, 6 ft in longitude, and 26 ft in altitude. The range residual characteristics indicate a closer match between full-ordered filter model and the real world (compared to current CIRIS). This difference is interpreted as a step towards the correct model of the real world error and an increase in overall filter accuracy. The magnitude of the increase in accuracy is well within the current CIRIS accuracy tolerances and are reasonable for this full-ordered model.

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